

SWISS LEGAL BENCHMARK FOR CLASSIFICATION AND
GENERATION

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"Hard work is worthless for those who don't believe in themselves."
— Naruto Uzumaki

ABSTRACT

We introduce four new datasets within the Swiss jurisdiction for two classification and two generative tasks and yielded significant insights into the domain of legal NLP. We discovered the predominance of comprehensive pre-training over model size in the classification tasks. In the generation tasks, larger models generally outperformed smaller ones, though the generated text often lacked in logical coherence. This exposes the current models' limitations and underlines the necessity for enhancements in these tasks. This research sets the stage for future investigations, emphasizing the potential of comprehensive pre-training and the improvement of logical coherence in legal language models.

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ACRONYMS

FSCS	Federal Supreme Court of Switzerland
NLP	Natural Language Processing
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
TC	Text Classification
BGE	Leading Decision
FSCS	Swiss Federal Supreme Court
CVG	Court View Generation
JP	Judgment Prediction
LAP	Law Area Prediction
SLAP	Sub Law Area Prediction
LDS	Leading Decision Summarization
GPT	Generative Pre-trained Transformer
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
SotA	State-of-the-Art
T5	Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer
LLMs	Large Language Models

Part I

THE BEGINNING

INTRODUCTION

The history of legal Natural Language Processing (NLP) is profound, with significant strides made in recent years [2, 21]. These advances are in part due to the introduction of legal datasets from a variety of global jurisdictions [6, 37] and the establishment of domain-specific tasks and benchmarks [4, 8, 13, 17, 18, 26, 34, 42, 45]. However, general benchmarks such as SuperGLUE [49] are reaching saturation, and their ability to effectively differentiate Legal Language Models is becoming questionable. This prompts an urgent need for larger and more challenging benchmarks, particularly in domain-specific contexts. Within Switzerland's context, the limited availability of datasets for evaluating Large Language Models (LLMs) restricts the comprehensive assessment of their performance within the country's diverse linguistic and legal landscape [33, 35].

In this thesis, we introduce four related datasets spanning two text classification and two text generation tasks within the jurisdiction of Switzerland. These datasets, derived from 26 cantons and the Swiss Federal Supreme Court (FSCS), represent a rich compilation of legal data within the multilingual and multi-jurisdictional Swiss context. Switzerland's multiple official languages and extensive data for its size position the country as a suitable testing ground for assessing LLMs in multilingual and multi-jurisdictional environments. Our evaluation focuses on two classification tasks, Judgment Prediction (JP) and Law Area Prediction (LAP) - and two generative tasks, CVG and LDS. In order to facilitate in-depth analysis and provide robust baselines for future research, we evaluate an array of models on our datasets, following the methodology akin to Hwang et al. [18] and Niklaus et al. [34].

This thesis is part of the SCALE Benchmark by me and friends [40].

BACKGROUND

2.1 THE TRANSFORMER MODEL

The Transformer is a deep learning model initially introduced by Vaswani et al. [48], in their groundbreaking paper, "Attention is All You Need". It was proposed to overcome the challenges faced by earlier sequence-to-sequence models like LSTM (Long short-term memory). The main innovation in the Transformer model is its self-attention mechanism that allows it to process the entire input sequence at once, as opposed to sequentially. This feature makes it a highly parallelizable model and efficient in handling long sequences. A typical Transformer model comprises an encoder and a decoder, each made up of a series of identical layers but serving different functions.

ENCODER The Encoder, the initial part of the model, processes the input data. Each encoder layer includes two components: a self-attention layer and a feed-forward neural network. The self-attention layer lets the encoder evaluate different words in the input sequence in their respective contexts, whereas the feed-forward network transforms the word embeddings. The encoder turns the input data into a sequence of continuous representations encompassing information from the whole input.

DECODER The Decoder's role is to generate the output data. It has a structure similar to the encoder, having a self-attention layer and a feed-forward neural network in each layer. However, an additional component in the decoder is a multi-head attention layer that operates on the encoder's output. This additional layer enables the decoder to concentrate on different sections of the input sequence, which is beneficial for tasks like machine translation where the sequence order of the input and output might not necessarily match.

2.2 FUNDAMENTAL MODELS

BERT Google's Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) [10] is a significant model in the field of NLP. Launched in 2018, BERT uses the Transformer's encoder mechanism in a bidirectional way, allowing it to analyze the context of each token in the input from both sides at once. BERT's architecture is initially trained on a large text corpus, and then it can be fine-tuned with an additional output layer for specific tasks. The initial training involves two tasks, Masked Language Modeling and Next Sentence Prediction, enabling BERT to understand both word-level and sentence-level representations. BERT has led to several variations, like RoBERTa [30] and

XLM [24]. RoBERTa, a model developed by Facebook, changes BERT's training process for improved results. On the other hand, XLM extends BERT's principles to multiple languages, making it a powerful tool for tasks involving several languages.

GPT The Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT), developed by OpenAI, is a unidirectional language model that uses a Transformer's decoder for all its operations. Its focus is to predict the next word in a sentence, given all the previous words within some text, which makes it particularly effective for text generation tasks. The GPT model is pretrained on a vast corpus of text data, and this pretraining involves learning to predict the next word in a sentence. Once pretraining is complete, GPT can then be fine-tuned for specific NLP tasks, such as text translation, question answering, or text summarization. The advancements in GPT's design and its increasing size have led to State-of-the-Art (SotA) performance across many NLP tasks, pushing the boundaries of what language models can achieve.

T5 The Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer (T5) [39] is an innovative model from Google Research, transforming traditional methods of NLP. T5 changes all NLP tasks into a unified "text-to-text" style, using a consistent model, objective function, and hyperparameters across a wide range of tasks. T5 uses a specific type of Transformer for both input and output conversion. During this process, each piece of text can refer to all the previous ones in the sequence. This structure allows T5 to manage many NLP tasks, including translation, summarization, sentiment analysis, and question-answering. T5's performance strongly depends on initial training on a large amount of text, where it learns to predict missing tokens in sentences. This is followed by specific fine-tuning for the particular task at hand.

RELATED WORK

3.1 TEXT CLASSIFICATION

3.1.1 *Judgment Prediction*

The domain of Legal Judgment Prediction (LJP) centers around the crucial task of predicting legal case outcomes given the provided facts. In the landscape of LJP research, there have been significant advances focusing on diverse languages, jurisdictions, and input types. Researchers have utilized a variety of datasets, each with their unique characteristics and annotations, to analyze and predict case outcomes [1, 5, 11, 32, 56]. In the context of Chinese criminal cases, notable efforts have been made by Xiao et al. [51, 52], where they utilized the CAIL2018 dataset, which consists of over 2.6M cases and provides annotations for Law Article, Charge, and Prison Term, among others. Focusing on the Indian and Swiss jurisdictions, Malik et al. [31] and Niklaus, Chalkidis, and Stürmer [33] and Niklaus, Stürmer, and Chalkidis [35] employed the ILDC and SJP datasets respectively, both using binary labels. European jurisdictions have been explored using the ECHR2019 and ECHR2021 datasets [5, 7]. The FCCR dataset, containing over 126K cases from France, has been used to predict Court Decisions with different setups, offering additional annotations such as the date of the court ruling and the law area [56]. Recently, Semo et al. [42] introduced a new perspective on LJP, applying it to US class action cases. The proposed task involves predicting the judgment outcome based on the plaintiff's pleas, further expanding the scope of LJP research and making the task more realistic. These efforts underscore the breadth of LJP research, demonstrating its applicability across multiple jurisdictions, languages, and legal systems, and its potential in assisting legal professionals and enhancing access to justice.

3.1.2 *Law Area Prediction*

Although not widely studied, several notable works have focused on LAP. Şulea et al. [56] worked on the Law Judgment Prediction (LJP) task, using a dataset of over 126K cases from the French Supreme Court. The study used Linear Support Vector Machines (SVMs) to classify cases into one of eight law areas, using the entire case description as input. This approach yielded an F1 score of 90%. Soh, Lim, and Chai [44] conducted a similar study using a dataset of 6K judgments in English from the Singapore Supreme Court. These judgments were mapped into 30 law areas. Several text classifiers were used in the study, achieving a macro F1 score of up to 63.2%.

3.2 TEXT GENERATION

3.2.1 *Court View Generation*

Over the past decade, text generation in the field of Legal NLP has been underexplored [20], especially in comparison to tasks such as classification and information extraction. The approach by Li and Zhang [27] utilizes Chinese case facts, as well as charge and law article information, to generate court opinions. A key difference from our task is the shortness of their opinions (avg. 31/34 tokens), while ours span approximately four thousand tokens on average. With the emergence of powerful generative models, we expect a surge in research activity in this area, necessitating challenging benchmarks to assess progress effectively.

3.2.2 *Leading Decisions Summarization*

In the field of legal text summarization, several noteworthy contributions have been made [12, 14, 19, 22], with the BillSum [23] and Multi-LexSum [43] datasets being particularly significant. The creators of the BillSum dataset focused on summarizing 22K bills from the US Congress and the state of California. They also applied transfer learning in summarization from federal to state laws. Models based on BERT and TF-IDF, as well as a combination of both, have been evaluated on this dataset. The BillSum dataset focuses on English language documents related to the US legislative environment. The Multi-LexSum dataset is another significant development in the area of legal text summarization. It targets long civil rights lawsuits, with an average length of over 75K words. This 9K-document dataset allows for in-depth study at different summary lengths: short (25 words), medium (130 words), and long (650 words), a unique feature of the Multi-LexSum dataset. Models based on BART [25] and PE-GASUS [54] were evaluated on this dataset. Like BillSum, the Multi-LexSum dataset is primarily for the English language and is relevant to the US legal setting.

Part II

THE SHOWCASE

DATASETS

4.1 TEXT CLASSIFICATION

See Table 1 for an overview of our datasets.

4.1.1 Judgment Prediction

We created the **Judgment** label by extracting the judgment outcome with regex patterns and assign a binary label with two classes: approval and dismissal, similar to [33]. For partially approved or dismissed judgments, we labeled them as approval or dismissal, respectively. Figure 1 shows the length distribution for the facts of the JP dataset.

Figure 1: Judgment Prediction facts length distribution

4.1.2 Law Area Prediction

The **Law Area** label was established by associating a law-area to each chamber where a case was adjudicated. Using metadata from Entscheidsuche.ch, a lawyer helped define the law areas for each

Table 1: Overview over all datasets and their multilingualism: Abbreviations: **C**antonal, **F**ederal, **F**acts, **C**onsiderations Column Fac and Cons report the mean token lengths. Sections Facts and Considerations are not available for Ruling Summarization due to different format, thus mean token length for the full text is reported and marked with *.

Name	Level	Total	DE	FR	IT	Fac	Cons
Law Area	Cant + Fed	329K	127K	156K	46K	2K	4K
Judgment Prediction	Cant + Fed	329K	160K	128K	41K	2K	4K
Court View	Cant + Fed	404K	197K	163K	44K	2K	5K
Court View Origin	Fed	270	49	221	-	1K	6K
Leading Decision Summarization	Fed	18K	12K	5K	835	-	*3K

chamber, resulting in chambers being classified into one of the four main law-area categories and 12 sub-law-areas. Due to many chambers operating in various law areas, it was not always feasible to assign a single law area label to each chamber. Particularly for the more detailed sub-law areas, where several chambers could not be uniquely linked, this resulted in a small subset of cases with the subset label. Initial results on the full dataset including the four main law areas showed that current models achieve near perfect accuracy, which is why we only consider the smaller filtered dataset of sub-areas for the purpose of this benchmark. Figure 2 shows the length distribution for the facts of the LAP dataset.

Figure 2: Law Area Prediction facts length distribution

4.2 TEXT GENERATION

4.2.1 Court View Generation

Clerks and judges dedicate a significant portion of their time to preparing considerations for court cases - approximately 50% in penal law and as much as an estimated 85% in other areas of law [33]. Crafting considerations is arguably the central task of a judge’s role, requiring intricate legal knowledge of applicable legislation, caselaw and legal analysis and advanced reasoning skills to connect this myriad of information. The complexity of this task, especially in the Supreme Court, is reflected in the average appointment age of judges being 50 years¹, underscoring the length and difficulty of their professional journey. Given these time and expertise demands, the necessity of the court view generation task emerges, aiming to create case considerations from the facts. Generating court views is challenging due to several reasons: Both the facts (input) and the considerations (output) can be long and complex. Current models, constrained by their limitations in handling long context, often fail to fully process this extensive input. This shortcoming, when coupled with the input’s inherent complexity, underscores the deficiencies of current models. Aiming to overcome these limitations, we present a novel Court View Generation dataset containing over 400K cases, covering a diverse range of legal scenarios. With an average length of 1522 tokens for

¹ Mit 28 Jahren Mitglied des Bundesgerichts, SonntagsZeitung, December 19, 2019, p. 24

the facts and 4673 tokens for the considerations, this dataset provides a challenging benchmark for models to generate coherent and accurate case considerations from legal facts. Furthermore, we provide a Court View origin dataset featuring federal rulings, enriched with data from the lower courts, including their facts and considerations, as well as those of the federal court. This provides a multilevel judicial perspective, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of case progression and further augmenting the challenge of court view generation. Figures 3 and 4 show the length distributions for the facts and the considerations of the CVG dataset respectively.

Figure 3: Court View Generation facts length distribution

Figure 4: Court View Generation considerations length distribution

4.2.2 *Leading Decisions Summarization*

Leading Decision (BGE) are crucial in the Swiss legal system, often cited to clarify legislative gaps. Access to their summaries simplifies searching and understanding key concepts, the most important citations, and main themes. In the LDS dataset, we include 18K BGE with their summaries, penned by FSCS clerks and judges. Figures 5 and 6 show the length distributions for the input text and the summary of the LDS dataset respectively.

Figure 5: Leading Decision Summarization input length distribution

Figure 6: Leading Decision Summarization summary length distribution

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

5.1 TEXT CLASSIFICATION

Model	Source	# Parameters	Vocab	Specs	Corpus	# Langs
MiniLM	[50]	118M	250K	1M steps / BS 256	2.5TB CC100	100
DistilBERT	[41]	135M	120K	BS up to 4000	Wikipedia	104
mDeBERTa-v3	[15, 16]	278M	128K	500K steps / BS 8192	2.5TB CC100	100
XLM-R _{Base/Large}	[9]	278M/560M	250K	1.5M steps / BS 8192	2.5TB CC100	100
mT5 _{Small/Base/Large}	[53]	300M/580M/1.2B	250K	1M steps / BS 1024	mC4 (CC)	101
X-MOD _{Base}	[38]	299M	250K	1M steps / BS 2048	2.5TB CC100	3 (81)
SwissBERT (XLM vocab)	[47]	299M	250K	364K steps / BS 768	Swissdox	3 (4)
Legal-Swiss-R _{Base}	ours	184M	128K	1M steps / BS 512	CH Rulings/Legislation	3
Legal-Swiss-R _{Large}	ours	435M	128K	500K steps / BS 512	CH Rulings/Legislation	3
Legal-Swiss-LF _{Base}	ours	208M	128K	50K steps / BS 512	CH Rulings/Legislation	3

Table 2: Models: All models can process up to 512 tokens, except Legal-Swiss-LF_{Base} which can process up to 4096 tokens. BS is short for batch size. # Parameters is the total parameter count (including the embedding layer). Our models were built upon the pre-trained roBERTa/Longformer. SwissBERT was further trained from pre-trained X-MOD. Utilizing three language adapters with X-MOD and SwissBERT led to fewer parameters and languages.

For our Text Classification (TC) tasks, namely LAP and JP, we adopted the setup proposed in the LEXTREME benchmark [34]. To be fair across languages, we computed the harmonic mean over all languages to arrive at the score per task. Furthermore, we evaluated SwissBERT [47], selected for its Swiss-specific pretraining data; X-MOD [38] and our custom pre-trained models, namely Legal Swiss RoBERTa and Legal Swiss Longformer (see Table 2).

5.2 TEXT GENERATION

For our experiments in text generation, we employed mT5 [53], a multilingual encoder-decoder model available in small, base, and large variants. We adopted an effective batch size of 16 using gradient accumulation when necessary. For evaluation we reported BERTScore [55], BLEU [36], METEOR [3], and ROUGE [28]. Each individual metric possesses inherent weaknesses [55], hence the necessity for employing multiple metrics for a more comprehensive assessment.

HYPERPARAMETERS For the main CVG dataset, we trained our models for only one epoch (because of the large training set) with a final batch size of 16, using gradient accumulation as needed. We performed evaluations every 1000 steps. For the smaller origin dataset, we increased the number of epochs to 100 and evaluated every 100 steps. For the LDS task, we adjusted the training to 10 epochs.

5.2.1 *Court View Generation*

We faced limitations due to lengthy input (avg. 1522 tokens) and output (avg. 4673 tokens) for CVG. To tackle these, we truncated input facts to 2048 tokens and output considerations to 512 tokens. In 90% of the cases, we were able to retain the complete facts. This decision was due to the substantial resources required for longer sequences and the task’s inherent difficulty, expected to be challenging even with only 512 output tokens. Furthermore, due to the large amount of test data and compute constraints, we limited our evaluation to a 1K-instance subset. For the origin dataset, the input was split evenly between origin facts and origin considerations.

5.2.2 *Leading Decision Summarization*

For our LDS experiments, similar to CVG, we dealt with substantial input text (avg. 3081 tokens), but shorter output text (avg. 168 tokens). To address these computational challenges, we truncated the input text to a maximum of 4096 tokens and the output texts to a length of 256 tokens, allowing us to preserve full output in over 80% of the cases.

RESULTS

Model	SLAP-SF	SLAP-SC	SJPXL-F	SJPXL-C
MiniLM	59.7 +/-3.8	61.1 +/-3.7	58.1 +/-0.4	78.5 +/-2.3
DistilBERT	63.7 +/-11.7	65.9 +/-6.4	59.9 +/-0.9	75.5 +/-3.3
mDeBERTa-v3	63.8 +/-6.3	59.3 +/-7.6	60.6 +/-0.9	77.9 +/-2.6
XLM-R _{base}	67.2 +/-15.9	73.4 +/-2.5	60.9 +/-0.6	79.7 +/-2.5
XLM-R _{large}	65.1 +/-8.5	78.9 +/-4.6	60.8 +/-0.6	80.9 +/-2.4
X-MOD _{base}	63.9 +/-10.1	64.4 +/-7.0	60.5 +/-0.6	79.1 +/-2.6
SwissBERT (xlm-vocab)	-	75.1 +/-5.2	61.4 +/-0.6	79.4 +/-2.5
Legal-ch-R _{base}	81.6 +/-2.6	83.0 +/-11.1	64.0 +/-1.3	86.4 +/-1.9
Legal-ch-R _{large}	80.4 +/-7.9	84.9 +/-9.9	62.8 +/-0.9	87.0 +/-2.3
Legal-ch-LF _{base}	80.2 +/-12.8	83.5 +/-11.4	65.4 +/-1.7	86.4 +/-1.8

Table 3: Results on the Text Classification datasets. Macro F1 score with standard deviation is reported. The 'F' or 'C' following the dash represents input based on 'Facts' or 'Considerations' respectively. 'SLAP' denotes Sub Law Area Prediction. Note: Seeds that yielded very high evaluation losses were considered as failed and therefore excluded from the analysis.

6.1 TEXT CLASSIFICATION

We present outcomes including standard deviations in Table 3. As anticipated, models with a larger parameter count typically deliver superior performance, with XLM-R_{large} leading the pack. The models we pre-trained, Legal-ch R_{Base} and Legal-ch R_{Large}, surpassed both XLM-R_{Base} and XLM-R_{Large}, implying that domain-specific pre-training can significantly enhance model performance. On the whole, our pre-trained models demonstrated superior outcomes in comparison to other models. Surprisingly, our Legal-ch-R_{Large} model was outperformed in 2 setups by our Legal-ch-R_{Base} model. This potentially indicates that comprehensive pre-training is more crucial than model size, which aligns with the conclusions of [29] and [46]. Despite additional training on expansive data, Legal-ch-LF did not exceed the hierarchical Legal-ch-R_{Base} model. The difference is largest in the JP and Sub Law Area Prediction (SLAP) tasks where the fine-tuned models are best.

Model	In Len \uparrow	Main Scores \uparrow				Origin Scores \uparrow			
		BERT	BLEU	MET	R ₁ / R ₂ / RL	BERT	BLEU	MET	R ₁ / R ₂ / RL
mT5Large	2048	75.74	66.92	34.44	<u>34.91/15.58/33.53</u>	76.24	62.59	32.25	34.80/16.11/33.58
mT5Large	1024	75.56	66.68	34.02	34.26/14.72/32.87	74.99	58.35	31.06	33.35/14.80/32.16
mT5Large	512	75.27	66.12	33.48	33.61/14.26/32.21	76.33	62.08	32.92	36.61/18.17/34.84
mT5Base	2048	75.01	65.48	32.89	33.23/13.57/31.89	75.99	63.39	34.15	36.48/ 18.81 /35.58
mT5Base	1024	75.15	65.73	33.15	33.49/13.96/32.18	76.07	60.99	33.50	<u>37.68/18.79/36.58</u>
mT5Base	512	74.89	65.55	32.66	32.66/13.16/31.35	76.08	62.21	32.80	36.40/17.58/34.98
mT5Small	2048	74.13	63.97	30.96	31.29/11.01/29.90	75.23	56.59	30.71	34.68/13.64/33.24
mT5Small	1024	74.00	63.70	30.68	31.05/10.77/29.64	75.75	58.99	31.17	34.62/14.25/33.91
mT5Small	512	73.92	63.83	30.57	30.58/10.35/29.20	75.63	61.12	32.33	35.16/14.45/33.72

Table 4: Results of Court View Generation task. ‘In Len’ denotes input length in tokens. **Bold**: best within model; underlined: best overall.

6.2 TEXT GENERATION

6.2.1 Court View Generation

We observed a clear trend in the performance of models across all scores, with larger models consistently outperforming smaller ones (see Table 4). However, the increase in performance with longer input was found to be minimal, and in some cases, counterproductive. Generally, the generated text displayed stylistic authenticity, resembling typical legal language. However, it often lacked logical coherence in terms of its content, which underscores the current models’ limited capacity to fully grasp the complexities of generating coherent court views. In numerous court cases, we observed a pattern where the target considerations contained similar paragraphs. These paragraphs were often predicted with a relatively good ability (see examples in Table 6). The results derived from the origin dataset were less conclusive. Likely due to the smaller dataset size, the outputs were found to be less indicative of the model’s capabilities.

6.2.2 Leading Decision Summarization

As expected, results in Table 5 for LDS task performance revealed two trends. Firstly, an increase in input length led to better scores across models. Secondly, larger models tend to outperform smaller ones, although the differences between the base and the large model are not sharply outlined. The quality of the generated text demonstrated a good stylistic imitation of legal language and a more consistent logical coherence compared to the CVG task (see examples in Table 7).

Model	In Len \uparrow	BERT \uparrow	BLEU \uparrow	MET \uparrow	R1 / R2 / RL \uparrow
mT5Large	4096	OOM	OOM	OOM	OOM
mT5Large	2048	73.10	27.21	21.88	31.47 / 12.22 / 29.94
mT5Large	512	70.67	26.89	18.31	24.76 / 6.15 / 23.48
mT5Base	4096	<u>73.33</u>	<u>30.81</u>	<u>23.50</u>	<u>32.43 / 12.78 / 30.87</u>
mT5Base	2048	72.45	30.13	21.94	30.09 / 10.79 / 28.71
mT5Base	512	70.60	27.10	18.31	24.72 / 6.15 / 23.55
mT5Small	4096	72.04	28.68	21.29	29.61 / 10.31 / 28.12
mT5Small	2048	71.38	24.64	19.28	27.88 / 9.19 / 26.54
mT5Small	512	69.66	20.73	15.95	22.91 / 5.36 / 21.85

Table 5: Results of Leading Decision Summarization task. ‘In Len’ denotes input length in tokens. **Bold**: best within model; underlined: best overall.

CONCLUSION

We introduced four tasks specifically designed for the Swiss legal system and evaluate multilingual models as a baseline. Even our pre-trained models tailored to the legal domain face significant difficulties in most of the tasks, particularly the challenging [CVG](#) and [LDS](#) task. This highlights the need for researchers to enhance existing models and track advancements in this field.

OUTLOOK

The political parties of the judges in the ruling determine in what direction the ruling will go. In future work, one could consider enriching the dataset with this information to improve the models performance in the [JP](#) task.

For simplicity, we treat the summary (regeste) of the leading decisions as just one string. Actually, it is composed of important citations in the first part, keywords from a [Thesaurus](#) in the second part and a text-based summary in the third part. The first two tasks could be framed as classification or retrieval tasks, possibly improving model performance.

Due to limited context width, we only considered the facts as input to the [CVG](#) task. However, judges and clerks do not only look at the facts when drafting a decision. They consider a myriad of information including possible lower court decisions and relevant case law, legislation and legal analyses. This information is available in our dataset. In the future, we see potential to develop systems that are capable of integrating all this information to write the legal reasoning.

Part III

APPENDIX

APPENDIX

A.1 RESULTS

A.1.1 Court View Generation

Table 6: Nine examples of generated considerations by mT₅_{Large} in comparison to the original considerations across three languages, showcasing high, average, and low scored outputs in CVG Task

Target	considerations: Erwägungen: 1. 1.1 Der angefochtene Entscheid ist in Anwendung von Sozialversicherungsrecht ergangen. Die Sozialversicherungsrechtliche Abteilung des Verwaltungsgerichts beurteilt gemäss Art. 57 des Bundesgesetzes vom 6. Oktober 2000 über den Allgemeinen Teil des Sozialversicherungsrechts (ATSG; SR 830.1) i.V.m. Art. 54 Abs. 1 lit. a des kantonalen Gesetzes vom 11. Juni 2009 über die Organisation der Gerichtsbehörden und der Staatsanwaltschaft (GSOG; BSG 161.1) Beschwerden gegen solche Entscheide. Die Beschwerdeführerin ist im vorinstanzlichen Verfahren mit ihren Anträgen nicht durchgedrungen, durch den angefochtenen Entscheid berührt und hat ein schutzwürdiges Interesse an dessen Aufhebung, weshalb sie zur Beschwerde befugt ist (Art. 59 ATSG). Die örtliche Zuständigkeit ist gegeben (Art. 58 ATSG). Da auch die Bestimmungen über Frist (Art. 60 ATSG) sowie Form (Art. 61 lit. b ATSG; Art. 81 Abs. 1 i.V.m. Art. 32 des kantonalen Gesetzes vom 23. Mai 1989 Urteil des Verwaltungsgerichts des Kantons Bern vom 6. Dez. 2022, UV/21/844, Seite 4 über die Verwaltungsrechtspflege [VRPG; BSG 155.21]) eingehalten sind, ist auf die Beschwerde einzutreten. 1.2 Anfechtungsobjekt bildet der Einspracheentscheid vom 5. November 2021 (act. II 45). Streitig und zu prüfen ist, ob die Beschwerdegegerin ihre Leistungen im Zusammenhang mit dem Ereignis vom 19. Juni 2020 zu Recht per 30. September 2020 eingestellt hat. 1.3 Die Abteilungen urteilen gewöhnlich in einer Kammer bestehend aus drei Richterinnen oder Richtern (Art. 56 Abs. 1 GSOG). 1.4 Das Gericht überprüft den angefochtenen Entscheid frei und ist an die Begehren der Parteien nicht gebunden (Art. 61 lit. c und d ATSG; Art. 80 lit. c Ziff. 1 und Art. 84 Abs. 3 VRPG). 2. 2.1 Die Zusprechung von Leistungen der obligatorischen Unfallversicherung setzt grundsätzlich das Vorliegen eines Berufsunfalles, eines Nichtberufsunfalles oder einer Berufskrankheit (Art. 6 Abs
Predicted	considerations: Erwägungen: 1. 1.1 Der angefochtene Entscheid ist in Anwendung von Sozialversicherungsrecht ergangen. Die Sozialversicherungsrechtliche Abteilung des Verwaltungsgerichts beurteilt gemäss Art. 57 des Bundesgesetzes über den Allgemeinen Teil des Sozialversicherungsrechts vom 6. Oktober 2000 (ATSG; SR 830.1) i.V.m. Art. 54 Abs. 1 lit. a des kantonalen Gesetzes über die Organisation der Gerichtsbehörden und der Staatsanwaltschaft vom 11. Juni 2009 (GSOG; BSG 161.1) Beschwerden gegen solche Entscheide. Die Beschwerdeführerin ist im vorinstanzlichen Verfahren mit ihren Anträgen nicht durchgedrungen, durch den angefochtenen Entscheid berührt und hat ein schutzwürdiges Interesse an dessen Aufhebung, weshalb sie zur Beschwerde befugt ist (Art. 59 ATSG). Die örtliche Zuständigkeit ist gegeben (Art. 69 Abs. 1 lit. a des Bundesgesetzes über die Unfallversicherung vom 20. Dezember 1946 [UVG; SR 832.20]). Da auch die Bestimmungen über Frist (Art. 60 ATSG) sowie Form (Art. 61 lit. b ATSG; Art. 81 Abs. 1 i.V.m. Art. 32 des kantonalen Gesetzes über die Verwaltungsrechtspflege vom 23. Mai 1989 [VRPG; BSG 155.21]) eingehalten sind, ist auf die Beschwerde einzutreten. 1.2 Das Gericht überprüft den angefochtenen Entscheid frei und ist an die Begehren der Parteien nicht gebunden (Art. 61 lit. c und d ATSG; Art. 80 lit. c Ziff. 1 und Art. 84 Abs. 3 VRPG). 1.3 Der Beschwerdeführer hat am vorinstanzlichen Verfahren teilgenommen, ist durch den angefochtenen Entscheid besonders berührt und hat ein schutzwürdiges Interesse an dessen Aufhebung oder Änderung. Auf die Beschwerde ist einzutreten. 2. 2.1 Die Beschwerdegegerin hat die Bestimmungen auf den Anspruch auf Heilbehandlung und Taggeld in Form von Heilbehandlung zufolge ihrer im August 2021 (act. II 42 und 46) eingereichten medizinischen Berichte zutreffend wiedergegeben. Darauf wird verwiesen. 2.2 Nach der Rechtsprechung ist der Beschwerdeführer durch den angefochtenen Entscheid berührt und haben ein schutzwürdiges
Scores	BERT: 91.69, BLEU: 84.17, METEOR: 62.43, ROUGE-1/2/L: 75.49 / 65.78 / 75.49
Target	considerations: EN DROIT 1. Conformément à l’art. 134 al. 1 let. a ch. 2 de la loi sur l’organisation judiciaire, du 26 septembre 2010 (LOJ - E 2 05) en vigueur dès le 1 er janvier 2011, la chambre des assurances sociales de la Cour de justice connaît, en instance unique, des contestations prévues à l’art. 56 de la loi fédérale sur la partie générale du droit des assurances sociales, du 6 octobre 2000 (LPGA - RS 830.1) relatives à la loi fédérale sur l’assurance-invalidité du 19 juin 1959 (LAI - RS 831.20).!endif>!if> Sa compétence pour juger du cas d’espèce est ainsi établie. 2. À teneur de l’art. 1 al. 1 LAI, les dispositions de la LPGA s’appliquent à l’assurance-invalidité (ci-après : AI), à moins que la loi n’y déroge expressément.!endif>!if> Toutefois, les modifications légales contenues dans la LPGA constituent, en règle générale, une version formalisée dans la loi de la jurisprudence relative aux notions correspondantes avant l’entrée en vigueur de la LPGA ; il n’en découle aucune modification du point de vue de leur contenu, de sorte que la jurisprudence développée à leur propos peut être reprise et appliquée (ATF 130 V 343 consid. 3). 3. Les modifications de la loi fédérale sur l’assurance-invalidité du 21 mars 2003 (4 ème révision), du 6 octobre 2006 (5 ème révision) et du 18 mars 2011 (révision 6a), entrées en vigueur le 1 er janvier 2004, respectivement, le 1 er janvier 2008 et le 1 er janvier 2012, entraînent la modification de nombreuses dispositions légales dans le domaine de l’assurance-invalidité.
Predicted	considerations: EN DROIT 1. Conformément à l’art. 134 al. 1 let. a ch. 4 de la loi sur l’organisation judiciaire, du 26 septembre 2010 (LOJ; RS E 2 05) en vigueur dès le 1 er janvier 2011, la Chambre des assurances sociales de la Cour de justice connaît, en instance unique, des contestations prévues à l’art. 56 de la loi fédérale sur la partie générale du droit des assurances sociales, du 6 octobre 2000 (LPGA; RS 830.1) relatives à la loi fédérale sur l’assurance-invalidité du 19 juin 1959 (LAI; RS 831.20).!endif>!if> Sa compétence pour juger du cas d’espèce est ainsi établie.!endif>!if> 2. Les dispositions de la LPGA s’appliquent à l’assurance-invalidité, à moins que la loi n’y déroge expressément.!endif>!if> Toutefois, les modifications légales contenues dans la LPGA constituent, en règle générale, une version formalisée dans la loi de la jurisprudence relative aux notions correspondantes avant l’entrée en vigueur de la LPGA; il n’en découle aucune modification du point de vue de leur contenu, de sorte que la jurisprudence développée à leur propos peut être reprise et appliquée (ATF 130 V 230 consid. 1.1; 335 consid. 1.2; ATF 129 V 4 consid. 1.2; ATF 129 V 4 consid. 1.2; ATF 127 V 467 consid. 1, 126 V 136 consid. 4b et les références). 3. A teneur de l’art. 17 al. 1 de la loi fédérale sur la partie générale du droit des assurances sociales, du 6 octobre 2000 (LPGA; RS 830.1), les modifications légales contenues dans la LPGA constituent, en règle générale, une version formalisée dans la LAI.
Scores	BERT: 91.27, BLEU: 85.8, METEOR: 68.12, ROUGE-1/2/L: 78.29 / 66.82 / 78.29

Target	<p>considerations: in diritto In ordine 2.1. La presente vertenza non pone questioni giuridiche di principio e non è di rilevante importanza (ad esempio per la difficoltà dell'istruttoria o della valutazione delle prove). Il TCA può dunque decidere nella composizione di un Giudice unico ai sensi dell'articolo 49 cpv. 2 LOG (STF 9C_699/2014 del 31 agosto 2015; 8C_855/2010 dell'11 luglio 2011; 9C_211/2010 del 18 febbraio 2011). Nel merito 2.2. Oggetto del contendere è sapere se a ragione l'Ufficio AI ha soppresso all'assicurato il diritto ad una rendita intera con effetto dal 1. settembre 2015 (cfr. consid. 1.3). L'insorgente postula l'annullamento della decisione impugnata del 10 maggio 2017 e quindi il mantenimento del diritto alla rendita intera. 2.3. Secondo l'art. 4 cpv. 1 LAI in relazione con gli art. 7 e 8 della LPGa, con invalidità s'intende l'incapacità al guadagno presunta permanente o di rilevante durata, cagionata da un danno alla salute fisica o psichica, conseguente ad infermità congenita, malattia o infortunio. Gli elementi fondamentali dell'invalidità, secondo la surriferita definizione, sono quindi un danno alla salute fisica o psichica conseguente a infermità congenita, malattia o infortunio, e la conseguente incapacità di guadagno. Occorre quindi che il danno alla salute abbia cagionato una diminuzione della capacità di guadagno, perché il caso possa essere sottoposto all'assicurazione per l'invalidità (Duc, L'assurance invalidité, in: Meyer (Hrsg.), Schweizerisches Bundesverwaltungsrecht, Band XIV, Soziale Sicherheit, 2a ed., Basilea/Ginevra/Monaco di Baviera 2007, pag. 1411, n. 46). Giusta l'art. 28 cpv.</p>
Predicted	<p>considerations: in diritto In ordine 2.1. La presente vertenza non pone questioni giuridiche di principio e non è di rilevante importanza (ad esempio per la difficoltà dell'istruttoria o della valutazione delle prove). Il TCA può dunque decidere nella composizione di un Giudice unico ai sensi degli articoli 26 c cpv. 2 della Legge organica giudiziaria civile e penale e 2 cpv. 1 della Legge di procedura per le cause davanti al Tribunale delle assicurazioni (cfr. STF 9C_211/2010 del 18 febbraio 2011; STF 9C_792/2007 del 7 novembre 2008; STF H 180/06 e H 183/06 del 21 dicembre 2007; STFA I 707/00 del 21 luglio 2003; STFA H 335/00 del 18 febbraio 2002; STFA U 347/98 del 10 ottobre 2001, pubblicata in RDAT I-2002 pag. 190 seg.; STFA H 304/99 del 22 dicembre 2000; STFA I 623/98 del 26 ottobre 1999). Nel merito 2.2. Oggetto della lite è sapere se l'Ufficio AI ha diritto alla rendita intera intera dal 1. settembre 2015 (doc. AI 122/445-450), a causa dell'invalidità della persona assicurata. Secondo l'art. 4 cpv. 1 LAI in relazione con gli art. 7 e 8 della LPGa, con invalidità s'intende l'incapacità al guadagno presunta permanente o di rilevante durata, cagionata da un danno alla salute fisica o psichica, conseguente a infermità congenita, malattia o infortunio. Gli elementi fondamentali dell'invalidità, secondo la surriferita definizione, sono quindi un danno alla salute fisica o psichica conseguente a infermità congenita, malattia o infortunio, e la conseguente incapacità di guadagno. Occorre quindi che il danno alla salute abbia cagionato una diminuzione della capacità di guadagno, perché il caso possa</p>
Scores	BERT: 86.57, BLEU: 81.39, METEOR: 65.76, ROUGE-1/2/L: 68.54 / 58.87 / 66.85
Target	<p>considerations: Das Bundesverwaltungsgericht zieht in Erwägung: 1. Nach Art. 53 Abs. 1 KVG kann gegen Beschlüsse der Kantonsregierungen nach Art. 39 KVG beim Bundesverwaltungsgericht Beschwerde geführt werden. Der angefochtene Beschluss Nr. 617/2019 des Regierungsrats des Kantons Zürich vom 26. Juni 2019 wurde gestützt auf Art. 39 KVG erlassen. Das Bundesverwaltungsgericht ist deshalb zur Beurteilung der Beschwerde zuständig (vgl. auch Art. 90a Abs. 2 KVG). Die Beschwerdeführerin hat am vorinstanzlichen Verfahren teilgenommen, ist als Adressatin durch den angefochtenen Regierungsratsbeschluss besonders berührt und hat insoweit an dessen Aufhebung beziehungsweise Abänderung ein schutzwürdiges Interesse (Art. 48 Abs. 1 VwVG). Sie ist daher zur Beschwerde legitimiert. Auf die frist- und formgerecht erhobene Beschwerde ist, nachdem auch der Kostenvorschuss rechtzeitig geleistet wurde, einzutreten (Art. 50 Abs. 1, Art. 52 Abs. 1 und Art. 63 Abs. 4 VwVG). Das Hauptrechtsbegehren der Beschwerdeführerin richtet sich auf Aufhebung der Ziffer I des Dispositivs des angefochtenen Beschlusses. Soweit sie dabei Bezug auf «C. Neue Regelung der Verlegungen ab Geburtshaus» nimmt, ist das im Lichte der Begründung der Beschwerde nicht so zu verstehen, dass sie auch die Aufhebung eines Teils der Begründung des angefochtenen Beschlusses beantragt. Der Antrag der Vorinstanz, auf die Beschwerde sei teilweise nicht einzutreten, weil sie sich auch gegen die Begründung des angefochtenen RRB richtet, ist daher unbegründet. 2. 2.1 Mit Beschwerde gegen einen Spitalistenentscheid im Sinne von Art. 39 Abs. 1 KVG kann die Verletzung von Bundesrecht unter Einschluss des Missbrauchs oder der Überschreitung des Ermessens und die unrichtige oder unvollständige Feststellung des rechtserheblichen Sachverhalts gerügt werden. Nicht zulässig ist hingegen die Rüge der</p>
Predicted	<p>considerations: Das Bundesverwaltungsgericht zieht in Erwägung: 1. 1.1 Gemäss Art. 31 des Verwaltungsgerichtsgesetzes vom 17. Juni 2005 (VGG, SR 173.32) beurteilt das Bundesverwaltungsgericht Beschwerden gegen Verfügungen nach Art. 5 des Verwaltungsverfahrensgesetzes vom 20. Dezember 1968 (VwVG, SR 172.021), sofern keine Ausnahme nach Art. 32 VGG vorliegt. Als Vorinstanzen gelten die in Art. 33 und 34 VGG genannten Behörden. Dazu gehören u.a. Verfügungen im Sinne von Art. 5 VwVG. Das Bundesverwaltungsgericht ist somit zuständig für die Beurteilung der vorliegenden Beschwerde und entscheidet auf dem Gebiet des Gesundheitsschutzes endgültig, ausser bei Eintreten auf einen Entscheid, der eine Verfügung im Sinne von Art. 5 VwVG betrifft. Eine Ausnahme nach Art. 32 VGG liegt nicht vor. 1.2 Das Bundesverwaltungsgericht ist zur Beurteilung der vorliegenden Beschwerde zuständig. 1.3. Gegen Entscheide des Regierungsrats ist ein Beschwerdeverfahren zulässig, wenn dieses eine Rechtsmittelinstanz ist und grundsätzlich der Rechtsschutzinteresse der Beschwerdeberechtigten gegeben ist (vgl. art. 32 VGG; BGE 138 II 274 E. 5.1 S. 280). 1.4 Das Bundesverwaltungsgericht wendet im Beschwerdeverfahren das Bundesrecht von Amtes wegen an (Art. 106 Abs. 1 des Bundesgesetzes vom 20. Dezember 1968 über das Verwaltungsverfahren [VwVG, SR 172.021]). Es wird gemäss Art. 62 Abs. 4 VwVG zur Beurteilung von Beschwerden in Zivilsachen gemäss Art. 82 Abs. 1 und Art. 86 Abs. 1 Bst. d bis Bst. e VwVG grundsätzlich nur geprüft, wenn diese vor Bundesgericht nicht mehr vorgetragen wurden und keine Verletzung des Opfers gegeben wurde. Das Bundesverwaltungsgericht wendet im Beschwerdeverfahren das Bundesrecht von Amtes wegen an. Es ist gemäss Art. 62 Abs. 4 VwVG an die Begründung der Begehren nicht gebunden und kann die Beschwerde auch aus anderen als den geltend gemachten Gründen gutheissen</p>
Scores	BERT: 75.72, BLEU: 67.17, METEOR: 31.26, ROUGE-1/2/L: 26.43 / 8.84 / 25.23
Target	<p>considerations: Considérant en droit: 1. Selon l'art. 5 al. 1 des dispositions du RPAC relatives à la Commission de recours individuel, la décision rendue par cette autorité peut faire l'objet d'un recours de droit administratif auprès du Tribunal cantonal dans les trente jours suivant la communication de la décision motivée, conformément à la loi cantonale du 28 octobre 2008 sur la procédure administrative (LPA-VD; BLV 173.36). D'après l'art. 92 al. 1 LPA-VD, le Tribunal cantonal connaît des recours contre les décisions et décisions sur recours rendues par les autorités administratives, lorsque la loi ne prévoit aucune autre autorité pour en connaître. En l'espèce, le recours a été déposé en temps utile (art. 5 al. 1 RPAC) et il satisfait aux autres conditions formelles de recevabilité (art. 75 al. 1 let. a, 79 al. 1 et 99 LPA-VD, applicables par renvoi de l'art. 5 al. 1 RPAC), si bien qu'il convient d'entrer en matière. 2. a) La classification salariale du poste qu'occupe le recourant est litigieuse en l'occurrence. b) L'organisation de l'administration fait partie des tâches propres des autorités communales (art. 2 de la loi vaudoise du 28 février 1956 sur les communes [LC; BLV 175.11]). Selon cette loi, il incombe au Conseil général ou communal de définir le statut des collaborateurs communaux et la base de leur rémunération (art. 4 al. 1 ch. 9 LC), la municipalité ayant la compétence de nommer les collaborateurs et employés de la commune, de fixer leur traitement et d'exercer le pouvoir disciplinaire (art. 42 al. 1 ch. 3 LC). Conformément à l'art. 33 al. 1 RPAC, le traitement du fonctionnaire comprend le traitement de base (let. a), les allocations</p>
Predicted	<p>considerations: Considérant en droit: 1. 1.1 Le personnel doit maintenir, par contrat de droit privé, une commune, un partenaire public, pour assurer la bonne exécution de leurs missions spéciales, ainsi qu'un minimum d'administration (art. 10 al. 1 du RPAC). L'art. 10 al. 2 RPAC prévoit que les fonctionnaires dans toute la ville de Lausanne sont soumis à la qualification communale et leur remplacement a lieu par des fonctions communales cantonales, comme applicable en la matière. Elle constitue en revanche une décision sujette à recours auprès de la juridiction compétente (art. 20 al. 2 et art. 30 al. 1 de la loi sur le personnel des communes du 15 novembre 1976 (LPAC)). 1.2 Selon la jurisprudence relative aux dispositions transitoires applicables au moment de la notification de la décision pour connaître du jugement du service, la décision de rémunération fait apparaître un changement de système de rémunération selon le RPAC. Cette disposition, qui comprend ainsi des critères objectifs et suffisants, permet au fonctionnaire de connaître de tous les aspects de la classification (Tappy, CPC, n. 1 ad art. 10 LPAC), ainsi que par le service de réduire son salaire. En l'espèce, l'autorité intimée a constaté que l'établissement des faits importants du dossier et de la satisfaction exigée sur le plan d'administration devait être complété dans la mesure où cela n'était pas possible, ce qui constituait effectivement un changement de système (Tappy, op. cit., n. 13 ad art. 10 LPAC). Il a constaté que le Service du personnel avait fixé le niveau de fonction attribué au fonctionnaire pour son titre de travail. Il a en outre estimé que cette classification était une décision de mise en œuvre déléguée à celui qui a entrepris une modification légale ou réglementaire du service. Parcon</p>
Scores	BERT: 75.74, BLEU: 66.19, METEOR: 31.69, ROUGE-1/2/L: 28.32 / 4.21 / 26.01

Target	considerations: Diritto: 1. Il ricorso in materia di diritto pubblico può essere presentato per violazione del diritto, così come stabilito dagli art. 95 e 96 LTF. Il Tribunale federale fonda la sua sentenza sui fatti accertati dall'autorità inferiore (art. 105 cpv. 1 LTF). Può scostarsi da questo accertamento solo qualora esso sia avvenuto in modo manifestamente inesatto, ovvero arbitrario (DTF 134 V 53 consid. 4.3 pag. 62), oppure in violazione del diritto ai sensi dell'art. 95 LTF (art. 105 cpv. 2 LTF). Salvo i casi in cui tale inesattezza sia lampante, la parte ricorrente che intende contestare i fatti accertati dall'autorità inferiore deve spiegare, in maniera circostanziata, per quale motivo ritiene che le condizioni di una delle eccezioni previste dall'art. 105 cpv. 2 LTF sarebbero realizzate (cfr. DTF 133 II 249 consid. 1.4.3 pag. 254 con riferimento). 2. Oggetto del contendere è sapere se sia lesivo del diritto federale il giudizio cantonale, che conferma la decisione su opposizione, la quale a sua volta nega all'assicurato le indennità per insolvenza per non avere rivendicato tempestivamente le proprie pretese salariali. 3. 3.1. Il Tribunale cantonale delle assicurazioni, esposto lo svolgimento del processo, le norme e la prassi ritenute applicabili, ha accertato che il ricorrente è stato legato da un contratto di lavoro con la ditta B. SA, dichiarata fallita il 15 maggio 2018, dal 15 aprile 2017 al 18 settembre 2017 come informatico e con un salario di fr. 3'360.- mensili. L'ultimo giorno di lavoro effettuato è stato il 1° settembre 2017. Il salario è stato saldato dal 15 al 30 aprile 2017. Per contro, non è stato pagato per i mesi di maggio, giugno, luglio e agosto, nonché per il 1° settembre 2017. Il
Predicted	considerations: Diritto: 1. 1.1. La procedura ricorsuale in materia di diritto pubblico è disciplinata dal diritto federale (art. 82 lett. a LTF) e dalla legge federale, in vigore dal 1° gennaio 2003, sull'assicurazione contro la disoccupazione: si tratta infatti di una causa di diritto pubblico contro una decisione finale adottata dalla Corte cantonale delle assicurazioni, entrata in vigore il 1° gennaio 2003. Il ricorso presentato dall'assoggettato al diritto di ricorrere (art. 89 cpv. 1 LTF) è di massima ammissibile dinanzi al Tribunale federale (art. 89 cpv. 1 LTF). 1.2. Il ricorso in materia di diritto pubblico può essere presentato per violazione del diritto, così come stabilito dagli art. 95 e 96 LTF, oltre che per violazione del diritto ai sensi dell'art. 95 LTF. Il Tribunale federale applica il diritto federale (art. 106 cpv. 1 LTF), senza essere vincolato né dai motivi adottati nel ricorso (art. 106 cpv. 2 LTF). Per contro, nel ricorso in materia di diritto pubblico il Tribunale federale esamina d'ufficio e con piena cognizione l'ammissibilità dei gravami che gli vengono sottoposti (DTF 133 III 439 consid. 1.3). 1.3. La critica del giudizio impugnato esplica degli effetti (art. 105 cpv. 1 LTF). Non è ammissibile che i ricorsi in materia di diritto pubblico possano essere decisi in base al diritto federale, ai sensi dell'art. 95 LTF, senza istruttoria (art. 97 cpv. 1 LTF, Art. 105 cpv. 2 LTF). 1.3. Il Tribunale federale esamina d'ufficio e con piena cognizione l'ammissibilità dei ricorsi che gli vengono sottoposti (DTF 133 III 439 consid. 1.3). 1.4. Con il ricorso in materia di diritto pubblico contro la decisione di primo grado, il Tribunale cantonale ha emesso
Scores	BERT: 75.79, BLEU: 66.28, METEOR: 30.29, ROUGE-1/2/L: 37.74 / 20.43 / 36.48
Target	considerations: Das Versicherungsgericht zieht in Erwägung: 1. Streitig und zu prüfen ist der Rentenanspruch der Beschwerdeführerin. - 3 - 2. Am 1. Januar 2022 sind die Änderungen betreffend Weiterentwicklung der IV (WEIV) in Kraft getreten. Weder dem IVG noch der IVV sind besondere Übergangsbestimmungen betreffend die Anwendbarkeit dieser Änderungen im Hinblick auf nach dem 1. Januar 2022 beurteilte mögliche Ansprüche des Zeitraums bis zum 31. Dezember 2021 zu entnehmen. Es sind daher nach den allgemeinen übergangsrechtlichen Grundsätzen jene Bestimmungen anzuwenden, die bei der Erfüllung des rechtlich zu ordnenden oder zu Rechtsfolgen führenden Tatbestands Geltung haben beziehungsweise hatten (vgl. Urteil des Bundesgerichts 8C_136/2021 vom 7. April 2022 E. 3.2.1 mit Hinweis unter anderem auf BGE 144 V 210 E. 4.3.1 S. 213). Da vorliegend Leistungen mit Anspruchsbeginn vor dem 1. Januar 2022 streitig sind, ist für deren Beurteilung die bis zum 31. Dezember 2021 geltende Rechtslage massgebend. 3. 3.1. Die Beschwerdegegnerin stützte sich in der Verfügung vom 14. Juni 2022 (Vernehmlassungsbeilage [VB] 162) in medizinischer Hinsicht im Wesentlichen auf das bidisziplinäre Gutachten der SMAB vom 3. August 2021 (VB 139; Fachdisziplinen: Neurologie und Psychiatrie). 3.2. Die SMAB-Gutachterinnen stellten in der interdisziplinären Gesamtbeurteilung die folgenden Diagnosen mit Auswirkungen auf die Arbeitsfähigkeit (VB 139.1 S. 6): "1. Neuropathische Schmerzen an der Innenseite des Mittelfingers links und der Handinnenfläche links (Schnittverletzung am Mittelfinger links mit initialer Nervenverletzung 19.11.2014, epineurale und weitere mehrfache operative Eingriffe 2014-2018), 2. Chronische Schmerzstörung mit somatischen und psychischen (ICD-10: F45.41)". Ohne Auswirkung auf die Arbeitsfähigkeit sei eine rezidivierende depressive Störung, gegenwärtig remittiert. Die Gutachterinnen hielten fest, insgesamt bestehe aufgrund der psychiatrischen und neurologi
Predicted	considerations: Das Gericht zieht in Erwägung: 1. Gemäss Art. 87 Abs. 2 des Bundesgesetzes über die Unfallversicherung (UVG) besteht Anspruch auf eine ganze Rente, wenn die versicherte Person mindestens zu 66 2/3 Prozent, auf eine halbe Rente, wenn sie mindestens zu 50 Prozent oder auf eine Viertelsrente, wenn sie mindestens zu 40 Prozent invalid ist. In Härtefällen besteht gemäss Art. 87 Abs. 2 UVG auch ein Anspruch auf eine halbe Rente, wenn sie mindestens zu 50 Prozent, wenn sie mindestens zu 40 Prozent invalid ist (Art. 8 Abs. 1 UVG). Anspruch auf eine Rente haben gemäss Art. 28 Abs. 2 des Bundesgesetzes über die Invalidenversicherung (IVG) Versicherte, die im Sinne von Art. 16 Abs. 1 IVG in Verbindung mit Art. 28 bis Abs. 1 IVG in Verbindung mit Abs. 1 und 2 IVG auch dann Anspruch auf eine Viertelsrente, wenn sie mindestens zu 40 Prozent invalid sind (Art. 28 Abs. 2 IVG i.V.m. Art. 16 ATSG). 2. 2.1 Anspruch auf eine Rente haben gemäss Art. 28 Abs. 1 IVG Versicherte, die: a. ihre Erwerbsfähigkeit oder die Fähigkeit, sich im Aufgabenbereich zu betätigen, nicht durch zumutbare Eingliederungsmassnahmen wieder herstellen, erhalten oder verbessern können; b. während eines Jahres ohne wesentlichen Unterbruch durchschnittlich mindestens 40 Prozent arbeitsunfähig (Art. 6 ATSG) gewesen sind; und c. nach Ablauf dieses Jahres zu mindestens 40 Prozent invalid (Art. 8 ATSG) sind. 2.2 Die Beschwerdeführerin bringt vor, die ärztlich eingeholten ärztlichen Berichte seien als diagnostisch zu qualifizieren. Das trifft vorliegend nicht zu. Ihr Gesundheitszustand sei gemäss Abklärungen vom RAD mit einer Invalidität von mindestens 40 Prozent zu vereinbaren. Die Leistungsfähigkeit sei in Art. 16 ATSG eingetreten. 2.2 Die Leistungsfähigkeit sei in Art. 16 ATSG i.V.m. Art. 28 Abs. 1 IVG
Scores	BERT: 62.42, BLEU: 51.67, METEOR: 19.69, ROUGE-1/2/L: 17.58 / 2.56 / 17.58
Target	considerations: le conseil de B. a rappelé que celle-ci contestait que son frère aurait été en droit de loger gratuitement au 1. dès le mois d'avril 2015. Afin d'éviter la notification d'une poursuite interruptive de la prescription, A. était invité à signer une déclaration de renonciation à la prescription concernant les loyers qui, selon B., étaient dus à la succession de leurs défunts parents. Etais annexée à ce courrier une déclaration de renonciation à invoquer la prescription libellée en ces termes : " Par la présente, A. déclare renoncer à invoquer toute exception de prescription vis-à-vis des successions de [feu D. et feu C.], eu égard à toutes prétentions éventuelles de loyers et charges alors qu'il logeait chemin 1. à Fribourg. Cette déclaration de renonciation est valable jusqu'au 31 décembre 2020. La présente déclaration ne vaut en aucun cas reconnaissance de dette ou de responsabilité quelconque. La présente déclaration n'a d'effet que si la prescription n'est pas déjà acquise à ce jour ". A. n'a pas donné suite à ce courrier. f. Par réquisition de poursuite du 7 avril 2020, reçue le lendemain par l'Office cantonal des poursuites de Genève (ci-après : l'Office), Me H., agissant en qualité de représentant du créancier, à savoir " Pour l'hoirie de feu C., décédée le 2019, Madame B. Rte 2. Fribourg ", a requis la poursuite de A., domicilié avenue 3. Genève, pour la somme de 112'500 fr. avec intérêts à 5% dès le 1er mai 2017, réclamée à titre de " Loyers et charges dus pour le logement du 1. à Fribourg d'avril 2015 à mai 2019 (50 x
Predicted	considerations: EN DROIT 1. 1.1 Le litige porte sur la désignation d'un représentant de la communauté héréditaire et la désignation d'un administrateur de la régie G. SA (art. 602 al. 3 CC). Le motif de la désignation du représentant est incontestable. Selon l'art. 602 al. 5 CC, la désignation d'un représentant de la communauté héréditaire est donc une décision de dernière instance cantonale au sens des art. 80 al. 1 et 82 al. 1 CPC, qui doit être notifiée à l'unique partie plaignante qui a pris part à la procédure (ATF 110 IV 92 consid. 1a; arrêt du Tribunal fédéral X. du 27 juillet 2004 ; ATF 99 III 58 consid. 1; ATF 118 la 397 consid. 1b; Tappy, CPC-VD, n. 3 ad art. 602 CC ; Replin, Le représentant de la communauté héréditaire, 5 ^{ème} éd., Lausanne 2013, p. 569; ATF 118 IV 286 consid. 2a; TF 6B_211/2007 du 29 janvier 2008, consid. 5.3; ATF 117 IV 29 consid. 3b; TF 8B_44/2007 du 15 août 2007, consid. 3.2; Tappy, Procédure civile, tome II, ad art. 602; Piquerez, in : Kuhn/Jeaneret [éd.], Basler Kommentar, n. 6 ad art. 602; TF 7B_51/2007 du 1 ^{er} janvier 2008, consid. 3.2; ATF 130 III 136 consid. 1.2.1; TF 9C_438/2007 du 30 septembre 2007, consid. 3.1; ATF 134 III 102 consid. 3.1; TF 6B_71/2007 du 24 août 2007, consid. 5b; TF 9C_792/2007 du 11 août 2007, consid. 4.2). 1.2 La désignation d'un représentant et de l'administration régulière de l'ensemble de la succession ont été rejetées. 2. 2.1. L'art. 602 al. 3 CC ouvre un recours au Tribunal cantonal, sans être lié par l
Scores	BERT: 63.90, BLEU: 46.65, METEOR: 19.12, ROUGE-1/2/L: 11.52 / 1.64 / 10.91

Target	considerations: A.c. Con progetto di decisione dell'8 gennaio 2014 l'UAI ha concluso, in via di riconsiderazione, per la soppressione della mezza rendita d'invalidità con effetto retroattivo al 30 aprile 2011. In sede di audizione, l'UAI ha esperito nuovi accertamenti, in particolare la perizia pluridisciplinare dell'8 aprile 2016. Con decisione del 14 luglio 2016 l'UAI ha riconosciuto che al momento dell'assegnazione della mezza rendita d'invalidità è incorso in un errore manifesto avendo applicato il "Prozentvergleich" in luogo del metodo ordinario di confronto dei redditi, da cui risulta un grado d'invalidità del 26 %. Ritenuta l'importanza della sua correzione, l'UAI, riconsiderando le decisioni 14 dicembre 2006 e 14 maggio 2007 nonché la comunicazione del 20 marzo 2009, ha predisposto la soppressione del diritto alla mezza rendita invalidità con effetto retroattivo al 30 aprile 2011. B. A. si è aggravato il 13 settembre 2016 al Tribunale delle assicurazioni del Cantone Ticino, che con giudizio del 17 maggio 2017 ha respinto il gravame. C. Il 19 giugno 2017 (timbro postale) A. inoltra un ricorso in materia di diritto pubblico al Tribunale federale, cui chiede di ammettere il ricorso e riformare il giudizio cantonale nel senso di confermare il diritto ad almeno una mezza rendita d'invalidità e ordinare all'UAI di versare tutte le prestazioni trattenute dal momento della revisione ad oggi. L'UAI e l'Ufficio federale delle assicurazioni sociali rinunciano a determinarsi. Diritto: 1. Il ricorso in materia di diritto pubblico può essere presentato per violazione del diritto così come stabilito dagli art. 95 e 96 LTF. Il Tribunale federale esamina d'ufficio l'applicazione de l diritto federale (art. 106 cpv. 1 L.
Predicted	considerations: Diritto: 1. Il Tribunale delle assicurazioni esamina d'ufficio e con piena cognizione l'ammissibilità dei gravami che gli vengono sottoposti (DTF 134 V 131 consid. 1.1 pag. 131; 133 V 477 consid. 1.1 pag. 481). In particolare, i gravami inoltrati già in tempo utile contro le decisioni di prima istanza rese dall'UAI in materia di assicurazioni sociali possono essere decisi sulla scorta degli atti, senza istruttoria (DTF 133 V 477 consid. 1.2 pag. 481). Il giudizio può essere reso sulla base degli atti, senza istruttoria (DTF 133 V 477 consid. 1.2 pag. 481; 133 V 477 consid. 1.2 pag. 481). 2. Il Tribunale delle assicurazioni esamina d'ufficio e con piena cognizione l'ammissibilità dei gravami che gli vengono sottoposti (DTF 133 V 477 consid. 1.2 pag. 481). 3. Giusta l'art. 4 cpv. 1 LAI in relazione con gli art. 7 e 8 della LPGA, con invalidità s'intende l'incapacità al guadagno presunta permanente o di rilevante durata, cagionata da un danno alla salute fisica o psichica, conseguente a infermità congenita, malattia o infortunio. Gli elementi fondamentali dell'invalidità, secondo la surriferita definizione, sono quindi un danno alla salute fisica o psichica conseguente a infermità congenita, malattia o infortunio, e la conseguente incapacità di guadagno. Occorre quindi che il danno alla salute abbia cagionato una diminuzione della capacità di guadagno, perché il caso possa essere sottoposto all'assicurazione per l'invalidità (DTF 134 V 329 consid. 3.2.3 pag. 331; 133 V 477 consid. 3.3.1 pag. 481; 129 V 4 consid. 1.2 pag. 5 con rinvii). 3.2. Giusta
Scores	BERT: 67.86, BLEU: 55.76, METEOR: 25.41, ROUGE-1/2/L: 24.32 / 5.59 / 23.65

A.1.2 Leading Decisions Summarization

Table 7: Three examples of generated summaries by mT5_{Base} in copmarison to the original summaries - with input length 4096, showcasing high, average, and low scored outputs in LDS Task

Target	regeste: Regeste Teilklage und negative Feststellungswiderklage (Art. 86 und 224 ZPO). Die Ausnahme vom Erfordernis der gleichen Verfahrensart gemäss Art. 224 Abs. 1 ZPO für negative Feststellungswiderklagen ist nicht auf den Fall beschränkt, dass es sich bei der Hauptklage um eine sogenannte echte Teilklage handelt, sondern gilt allgemein dann, wenn die Teilklage eine Ungewissheit zur Folge hat, die es rechtfertigt, die Feststellung des Nichtbestands einer Forderung oder eines Rechtsverhältnisses zu verlangen (E. 2).
Predicted	regeste: Regeste Voraussetzungen, unter denen eine Widerklage erhoben werden darf, wenn eine echte Teilklage beurteilt wird (E. 2.1). Zur Anwendung von Art. 224 Abs. 1 ZPO ist die Ausnahme vom Erfordernis der gleichen Verfahrensart gemäss Art. 224 Abs. 1 ZPO nicht auf diesen Fall beschränkt, sondern gilt allgemein dann, wenn die Teilklage eine Ungewissheit zur Folge hat, die es rechtfertigt, im Sinne von Art. 88 ZPO die Feststellung des Nichtbestands einer Forderung oder eines Rechtsverhältnisses zu verlangen (E. 2.2).
Scores	BERT: 88.03, BLEU: 30.45, METEOR: 43.78, ROUGE-1/2/L: 72.44 / 54.05 / 70.87
Target	regeste: Regeste Uferschutzplanung Wohlensee; Gesamtinteressenabwägung. Die Behörden nehmen bei der Genehmigung einer Sondernutzungsplanung eine umfassende Interessenabwägung vor (vgl. Art. 3 RPV ; E. 3.2). Würdigung des Gutachtens der Vogelwarte Sempach und der Stellungnahme des BAFU als Fachbehörde (E. 5.5, 6.3 und 6.4). Im zu beurteilenden Fall wird das öffentliche Interesse an einer ufernahen Wegführung (vgl. Art. 3 Abs. 2 lit. c RPG) relativiert, weil ein durchgehender Sichtschutz zum Schutz der im Gebiet vorkommenden Vogelarten erforderlich wäre, was Spaziergänger das Erleben der Uferlandschaft nur sehr beschränkt ermöglichen würde (E. 6.5 sowie 3.3). Das Gebiet des Wohlensees stellt eines von insgesamt 25 Wasser- und Zugvogelreservaten von nationaler Bedeutung dar (vgl. Art. 11 Abs. 2 JSG, Art. 2 Abs. 1 i.V.m. Anhang 1 WZVV).
Predicted	regeste: Regeste Art. 3 Abs. 2 lit. c RPG ; schweizerische Vogelwarte Sempach; Umweltschutz. Gutachten im Bereich des Umweltschutts, insbesondere von dem UVG/USG ergangenen Streitwert (E. 3.1). Ein öffentlicher Weg, der über Privatgrundstücke führt und mit dem Enteignungsrecht zugunsten des Gemeinwesens verbunden ist, stellt eine öffentlich-rechtliche Eigentumsbeschränkung dar (E. 3.3). Interessenabwägungen sind grundsätzlich frei (E. 3.4 und 3.5). Umfang des geplanten Uferweges; ein ausweisesenes öffentliches Interesse an einem direkt dem Ufer entlangführenden Weg sowie an einer zumindest ufernahen Wegführung (E. 3.5).
Scores	BERT: 73.91, BLEU: 47.21, METEOR: 30.91, ROUGE-1/2/L: 32.75 / 10.63 / 32.75
Target	regeste: Regeste a Schwere Bedrängnis, grosse seelische Belastung und heftige Gemütsbewegung; Art. 48 lit. a Ziff. 2 und Art. 48 lit. c StGB. Abgrenzung dieser Strafmilderungsgründe untereinander (E. 2.1-2.3). Regeste b Mord, heftige Gemütsbewegung und grosse seelische Belastung; Art. 48 lit. c und Art. 112 StGB. Die für den Mord typische Skrupellosigkeit schliesst die Bejahung der Strafmilderungsgründe der heftigen Gemütsbewegung und der grossen seelischen Belastung aus (E. 2.5).
Predicted	regeste: Regeste Art. 112 und 49 Abs. 2 StGB ; tiefe Gewalt, Schwere Gewalt, Mord. Die Beeinträchtigung oder der schwere Gewalt ist einen psychischen Klumpen im Sinne des Art. 48 StGB, wenn beide Personen einen Beziehungskonflikt bilden und sich ein bestimmtes Verhältnis zwischen einseitigen Umständen des Tatgehens und der Begründung der Tatbegehren haben (E. 2 und 3).
Scores	BERT: 69.3, BLEU: 12.14, METEOR: 14.72, ROUGE-1/2/L: 30.43 / 10.26 / 30.43

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ERKLÄRUNG

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